

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF A MOTORIZED TWO-ROW MULTISEED GRAIN WALKING PLANTER

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ABSTRACT

This study details the performance evaluation of a motorized two-row multiseed grain walking planter intended for small-scale farmers. The planter maximizes crop yields, minimizes labour demands, and improves field efficiency. Results obtained from field test revealed that the seed planter recorded mean theoretical field capacity value of 0.2683 ha/h, mean effective field capacity value of 0.2447 ha/h, mean field efficiency value of 90.80%, mean intra-row spacing distance of 334.04 mm and fuel consumption value of 2.43 l/ha. More so, the theoretical field capacity values obtained ranged from 0.1949 to 0.3228 ha/h, effective field capacity values obtained ranged from 0.1727 to 0.3024 ha/h; field efficiency values obtained ranged from 88.62 to 93.67%; intra-row spacing distance values obtained ranged from 333 mm to 334.91 mm; and fuel consumption values obtained ranged from 1.95 l/ha to 2.98 l/ha. The planter's forward speed have positive correlation with theoretical field capacity, effective field capacity, field efficiency, inter-row spacing and fuel consumption, hence improving agricultural productivity and efficiency. This study advances the creation of efficient agricultural technology, catering for small-scale farmers' requirements and enhancing food security. It was recommended that future research should focus on improving the seed planter's mobility and integrating advanced technologies.

Keywords: Agricultural Machinery, Labour Efficiency, Mechanized Grain Planter, Smallholder Agriculture, Crop yield

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of agricultural machinery has revolutionized farming practices, transforming the way grains are planted and cultivated. The motorized two-row multiseed grain walking planter represents a significant advancement in this field, combining cutting edge technology with traditional agricultural methods. This innovative equipment offers farmers a flexible and effective solution to enhance their planting processes, exemplifying a new era of agricultural efficiency and sustainability. The integration of precision planting mechanisms and multifunctionality in the motorized two-row multiseed grain walking planter optimizes planting operations, enhances productivity, and promotes resource efficiency. By facilitating the concurrent planting of two rows of grains, this planter doubles the planting capacity of the conventional single-row planters, expediting the planting process while ensuring consistent spacing and depth of planting. This results in improved crop emergence and overall production potential. The multiseed planter has the capability of delivering the seeds precisely with uniform depth in the furrow, and also with uniform spacing between the seeds.

Ikechukwu *et al.* (2014) developed a planter that functioned properly as expected with a planting capacity of 0.0486 ha/h. The planter was not motorized and the seed metering mechanism was made from wood. Adesoye and Mary (2015) developed a planter that had field efficiency and field

capacity of 76.3% and 0.39 ha/h, respectively, with seed rate of 0.25 kg/ha, 0.18 kg/ha and 0.21kg/ha at different conditions. Ani *et al.* (2016) designed a planter which recorded a metering efficiency of 88.94%, effective field capacity of 0.27 ha/h and field efficiency of 71.86% during the planter's evaluation.

Mechanization has transformed the agricultural sector, with varying degrees of adoption across different regions. Planting, a critical process in farming, involves sowing seeds in the soil to optimize germination outcomes. Over time, planting techniques have evolved from manual methods to incorporate tools and machines. Research highlights the importance of developing small-scale cultivation technologies that cater for the needs of small farms, prioritize user-friendly design, and enhance planting efficiency while reducing labour requirements. The development of a motorized two-row multiseed grain walking planter addresses the challenges faced by smallholder farmers, providing a mechanized planting solution that is adaptable to small-scale farming systems, enhances planting efficiency, and promotes sustainable agriculture practices.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Description of the Planter

The two-row multiseed grain walking planter have some essential components such as the basic frame, seed metering system, seed hoppers, ground wheels, furrow openers, and furrow coverer. The primary specifications of this motorized two-row multiseed grain walking planter include dimensions measuring 1,845 mm, 1,015 mm and 1,495 mm for the planter's length, width and height, respectively; plant-to-furrow spacing within rows ranging from 25 to 40 cm and between rows from 20 to 90 cm; and a built-in handle for controlling the direction of the seed planter during planting operation. The seed metering system of the planter is vertically inclined with various holes inserted for providing the desired seed sowing distance. To ensure accurate seed placement and a reduce movement between the feeding mechanism and the planter's wheel having a diameter size of 39 cm, a transmission system was designed to control the number of seed drops per revolution using diverse metering seed plates at a sprocket ratio of 1:1. The front column has a fixed furrow opener that allows one to regulate and change the furrow's depth. Two cage wheels make up the closing mechanism, which presses the seeds into the ground while the planter is moving as shown in Figure 1. Presented in Figure 2 is the planter's orthographic projection and 3D view.

Figure 1. Pictorial view of the closing mechanism of the seed planter

Figure 2. Orthographic projection and 3D view of the motorized two-row multiseed grain walking planter

2.2 Description of the Study Area

The study was carried out at the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM), Ilorin, Kwara State which is located at 370 m above sea level in the Southern Guinea Savanna ecological zone of Nigeria by Longitude 4° 30'E and Latitude 8° 26'N. The soil in the test location of the study area was classified as Alfisols (Soil Survey Staff, 1975) under the USDA soil order.

2.3 Particle Size Analysis

Particle size analysis was carried out using the hydrometer method described by Gee and Or (2002). Sodium hexametaphosphate (calgon) was used as the dispersant. The textural class of the soil was determined using the USDA Textural Triangle.

2.4 Experimental Field Layout

The experimental field used for the test was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD). The field was ploughed and harrowed and later cleared of surface debris and impediments. Nine experimental plots with each measuring 30 meters by 10 meters, were created in the experimental field. The mean values of the three planting speeds used for evaluating the seed planter were used in assessing the performance of the seed planter.

2.5 Test Crop

Maize was used for testing the motorized two-row multiseed grain walking planter. The maize was purchased from Ganmo market in Ilorin, Kwara State.

2.5.1 Seed viability

Seed viability test was carried out on the maize seed purchased from Ganmo market. The seed viability test which involve placing 20 maize seeds at a time in water solution gave a viability value of 98.33%. This indicates almost all the seeds purchased from Ganmo market were viable.

2.6 Test Parameters

The parameters considered for use in assessing the performance of the motorized two-row multiseed grain walking planter include theoretical field capacity (TFC), effective field capacity (EFC), field efficiency (FE), intra-row spacing distance and fuel consumption. FC presented an area of land processed per unit time for a particular site operation, FE defined effective and theoretical site capacity as the ratio of expected and actual time required to complete the site operation (Dagnachew *et al.*, 2017).

2.6.1 Theoretical field capacity (TFC)

This is the maximum area that a grain planter can cover at a given time, under ideal conditions. Accurate theoretical field capacity determination is crucial for optimizing planter performance and productivity and is calculated using the expression given by Ram and Mishra (2020) and Science *et al.* (2021) as:

$$\text{TFC (ha/h)} = \frac{\text{Harvesting speed (km/h)} \times \text{Harvesting width (m)}}{10,000} \quad (1)$$

2.6.2 Effective field capacity (EFC)

This describes the actual area that the planter can cover in a specific amount of time, accounting for variables like: planting speed, crop density and yield, field topography and soil conditions, machine efficiency and downtime. Effective field capacity is calculated using the expression given in Equation (2).

$$\text{Effective field capacity (ha/h)} = \frac{\text{Area of land (ha)}}{\text{Time taken (h)}} \quad (2)$$

2.6.3 Field efficiency

According to Andrew *et al.* (2024), this was computed using the proportion that exist between the effective and theoretical field capacities.

$$\text{FE} = \frac{\text{EFC}}{\text{TFC}} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

where,

FE = Field efficiency, (%)

EFC = Effective field capacity, (ha/h)

TFC = Theoretical field capacity, (ha/h)

2.6.4 Fuel consumption

The fuel required for each planting operation was determined by filling the tank to full capacity before and after the test. Amount of refueling after each test is the fuel consumption for the test. The filling of fuel tank before the operation and then refilling after completing the operation in determining the amount of fuel consumed during operation is a common method used in the field for determining fuel consumption in litres per hectare for any field machinery powered by an engine. This same method was as reported by (Ajav and Adewoyin, 2011; Ikpo and Ifem, 2005; Kudabo and Gbadamosi, 2012; Meshack-Hart, 1997; Sirelkatim *et al.*, 2001; Udo and Akubuo, 2004) in determining tractor fuel consumption in litres per hectare.

Fuel consumption measured in either L/ha or L/h was expressed mathematically as:

$$\text{Fuel consumption } \left(\frac{\text{l}}{\text{ha}}\right) = \frac{\text{Volume of fuel consumed (l)}}{\text{Area of field (ha)}} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Fuel consumption } \left(\frac{l}{h}\right) = \text{Fuel consumption } \left(\frac{l}{ha}\right) \times \text{Effective field capacity } \left(\frac{ha}{h}\right) \quad (5)$$

2.7 Soil Parameter

2.7.1 Soil moisture

Klenin et al. (1985) defined soil moisture content as the amount of liquid, usually water that is present in the soil. It is expressed as a percentage of the mass of water in the soil to the mass of the dried soil (for dry weight classification). The soil moisture content (in dry basis) measured in%, can be expressed mathematically as:

$$M_c = \frac{W_w}{W_s} \times 100\% \quad (6)$$

where,

Mc = Soil moisture content (%)

Ws = Mass of oven dried soil (g)

Ww = Mass of water present in soil (g)-

2.8 Laboratory Performance of the Grain Planter

Tests were carried out in the laboratory prior to subjecting the seed planter to field test. Analysis were carried out on the pattern of dropping, number of seeds per drop, spacing between seeds etc. Presented in Figure 3 is the pictorial view of the motorized two-row multiseed grain walking planter.

Figure 3. Pictorial view of the motorized two-row multiseed grain walking tractor

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

Table 1 displays the findings from the soil characterization utilized in the field used for testing the grain planter. Table 2 provides information concerning depth of planting, capacity of the seed and fertilizer hopper, number of seeds per drop, percentage of missing plants, percentage of double picking, height of the ridge, depth of fertilizer placement, and planter's efficiency at three different working tractor speeds. Table 3 displays the performance of the motorized two-row multiseed grain walking planter. Table 4 displays the descriptive analysis of the results obtained during field evaluation of the planter.

Table 1. The Soil Characterizations used for the Field Evaluation

S/No.	Parameters	Result
1	Soil type	Loamy sandy
2	Soil moisture content	8.54% (db)
3	Method of sowing	center to center
4	Size of each plot	30 x 10 m
5	Number of plot	9

Table 2. Specific information obtained for the motorized two-row multiseed walking grain planter

Parameters	Result
Minimum number of seeds dropped	1
Maximum number of seeds dropped	3
Working speed of the planter (km/h)	1.92
Intra-row spacing obtained (mm)	380, 310, 300, 320, 360, 330, 320, 360, 350 and 300
Average intra-row spacing obtained (mm)	333
Standard deviation obtained for intra-row spacing using theoretical planting distance as mean (mm)	301.71 ± 43.21
Deviation in terms of percentage value	14.32
Standard deviation obtained for intra-row spacing using average intra-row spacing value as mean (mm):	333 ± 27.91
Deviation in terms of percentage value	8.38
Number of intra-row spacing readings obtained that fell above the theoretical planting distance of the planter	8
Number of intra-row spacing readings obtained that fell below the theoretical planting distance of the planter	2

Table 3. Performance evaluation of the motorized two-row multiseed walking grain planter

*Parameters	Speed of planter during operation (km/h)		
	1.92	2.60	2.92
Depth of planting (mm)	43.18	43.18	43.18
Intra-row distance (mm)	333	334.2	334.91
Uncovered seeds (%)	5.1	5.8	6.2
Missing hills (%)	3.7	4.3	4.98
Fuel consumption (l/h)	0.34	0.61	0.91
Fuel consumption (l/ha)	1.95	2.36	2.98
Sound level (dB)	62.21	62.83	63.51
Area of land (ha)	0.03	0.03	0.03
Time of operation (h/ha)	5.79	3.86	3.31
Theoretical field capacity (ha/h)	0.1949	0.2873	0.3228
Effective field capacity (ha/h)	0.1727	0.2589	0.3024
Field efficiency (%)	88.61	90.11	93.68

* mean values obtained for three replications

Table 4. Descriptive statistics of the results obtained during field performance of the grain planter

Test parameters	N	Min.	Max.	Mean	STD
Intra-row space distance (mm)	3	333.00	334.91	334.0367	.96542
Uncovered seed (%)	3	5.10	6.20	5.7000	0.55678
Missing hills	3	3.70	4.98	4.3267	0.64042
Fuel consumption (l/ha)	3	1.95	2.98	2.43	0.51856
Fuel consumption (l/h)	3	0.34	0.91	0.62	0.28513
Sound level (dB)	3	62.21	63.51	62.8500	0.65023
Time of operation (h/ha)	3	3.31	5.79	4.32	1.30242
Theoretical field capacity (ha/h)	3	0.1949	0.3228	0.2683	0.06603
Effective field capacity (ha/h)	3	0.1727	0.3024	0.244667	0.06601
Field Efficiency (%)	3	88.62	93.67	90.80	2.59474

4.2 Discussion

4.2.1 Determination of theoretical field capacity

The average values of the theoretical field capacity obtained considering the three different speeds used during the evaluation process of the planter in the field varied from 0.1949 to 0.3228 ha/h. The mean theoretical field capacity value obtained was 0.2683 ha/h with a standard deviation value of 0.06603 ha/h. The planter's theoretical field capacity demonstrates that the planter speed has a considerable impact. The outcome as shown in Figure 4 demonstrates that the planter's field efficiency increases as the planter's speed increases.

Figure 4. Bar chart showing the effect of planter’s speed on theoretical field capacity

4.2.2 Determination of effective field capacity

The average values of the effective field capacity obtained considering the three different speeds used during the evaluation process of the planter in the field varied from 0.1727 to 0.3024 ha/h. The mean effective field capacity value obtained was 0.2447 ha/h with a standard deviation value of 0.06601 ha/h. The effective field capacity of the planter as shown in Figure 5 showed that the planter speed has effect on the effective field capacity.

The effective field capacity which contrasts with theoretical field capacity, accounted for real-world factors such as obstacles and turning time, offering a more realistic assessment of the planter’s productivity.

Figure 5. Bar chart showing the effect of planter speed on effective field capacity

4.2.3 Determination of intra-row spacing distance

The intra-row spacing distance obtained varied narrowly from 333 to 334.91 mm with a mean value of 334.04 mm. It also gave a low standard deviation value of 0.97 mm, suggesting consistent spacing along the row while planting. The intra-row spacing of the planter as shown in Figure 6 shows that the planter’s speed has effect on the intra-row spacing distance of the planted maize.

Figure 6. Bar chart showing the effect of the planter speed on intra-row spacing distance

4.2.4. Determination of field efficiency of the planter

The average values of the field efficiency obtained considering the three different speeds used during the evaluation process of the planter in the field varied from 88.62% to 93.67%. The mean field efficiency value obtained was 90.80% with a standard deviation value of 2.59%. It can be deduced from Figure 7 during planting operation that the planter's field efficiency increases as the planter's speed increases.

Figure 7. Bar chart showing the effect of planter's speed on field efficiency

4.2.5 Determination of fuel consumption

The seed planter's fuel consumption values obtained in the field ranged from 1.95 to 2.98 l/ha. The mean fuel consumption value obtained was 2.43 l/ha while the standard deviation value obtained was 0.52 l/ha. This demonstrates a moderate fuel usage. Figure 8 shows that the planter's fuel consumption value increases as the planter's speed increases during operation.

Figure 8. Bar chart showing the effect of planter's speed on fuel consumption

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

Field performance evaluation was carried out on a motorized two-row multiseed grain walking planter which was developed by the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM), Ilorin. Results obtained from the field evaluation showed that there exist a positive correlation between the planter's speed and other measured parameters such as theoretical field capacity, effective field capacity, field efficiency, intra-row spacing distance and fuel consumption. The developed motorized two-row multiseed grain walking planter recorded effective field capacity values which ranged from 0.1727 ha/h to 0.3024 ha/h, theoretical field capacity values which ranged 0.1949 ha/h to 0.3228 ha/h, field efficiency values which ranged 88.62% to 93.67%, fuel consumption values which ranged from 1.95 l/ha to 2.98 l/ha and intra-row spacing distance values which ranged from 333 mm to 334.99 mm. The planter attained an average planting depth of 43.18 mm. The motorized two-row multiseed grain planter provides an effective means of maximizing crop yields, minimizing labour expenses, and improving food security.

5.2 Recommendations

Though, this study actually met its goals, however, additional research is required to improve on the planter's agility which will make the seed planter more user-friendly and suitable for use in the different terrains in Nigeria. Further research on the seed planter's should focus on:

1. Enhancing the planter's stability and equilibrium.
2. Incorporating sophisticated technologies, like precision agriculture and automation.
3. Executing field testing under varied environmental circumstances.
4. Assessing the planter's compatibility with alternative grain crops.

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